

Domain Invariance Theorem

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Author: Giuseppe Casillo

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Abstract

We present a self-contained proof of Brouwer's Invariance of Domain Theorem, starting from Borsuk's theorem and Brouwer's fixed point theorem. Several intermediate results are established, including dimension invariance, non-retractability of spheres, and a zero-stability lemma.

1 Introduction

In this paper we prove the Domain Invariance Theorem, which states:

Let U be a open subset of \mathbb{R}^n (with respect to the standard topology) and $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ a continuous and injective function. Then $V = f(U)$ is open in \mathbb{R}^n and f is a homeomorphism between U and V .

Throughout the paper we will use several auxiliary results, and we will also make use of results from algebraic topology, such as Borsuk's theorem. The reader is assumed to be familiar with definitions and theorems from general topology before proceeding.

2 Brouwer's Fixed Point Theorem

We define $B^n = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|x\| \leq 1\}$, the n -dimensional "ball" of radius 1, and $S^n = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|x\| = 1\}$, the n -dimensional sphere of radius 1. In this section we will use **Borsuk's theorem**:

There are no continuous maps $f : S^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $f(-x) = -f(x) \forall x \in S^{n+1}$

We omit the proof and derive the following consequences:

Corollary 2.1.1: For every continuous map $f : S^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\exists x \in S^n$ such that $f(x) = f(-x)$.

Proof. For $n = 0$, the proof is trivial! Indeed, \mathbb{R}^0 is the vector space consisting only of the zero element (which we shall call x_0), and $S^0 = \{x \in \mathbb{R} : |x| = 1\}$. Hence, there exists a unique function, which is also continuous²: $\tilde{f} : S^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^0$, satisfying $\forall x \in S^0, \tilde{f}(x) = x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^0$. Therefore $\forall x \in S^0, \tilde{f}(x) = \tilde{f}(-x)$. We continue the proof for $n \geq 1$.

Suppose for contradiction that $f(x) - f(-x) \neq 0 \forall x \in S^n$. Then the map:

$$g : S^n \rightarrow S^{n-1}, g(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(-x)}{\|f(x) - f(-x)\|}$$

is continuous, being a composition of continuous functions³, its image lies in S^{n-1} since the image of $f(x)$ is in \mathbb{R}^n , and finally it satisfies $g(-x) = -g(x) \forall x \in S^n$, in contradiction with Borsuk's theorem.

□

From this we obtain the well-known:

2.1 Dimension Invariance Theorem:

Given $m < n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ a nonempty open set, every continuous map $f : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is not injective.

¹The norm is the standard norm of \mathbb{R}^n .

²The function that sends every point of S^0 to the unique point of \mathbb{R}^0 .

³The function is well defined on all of S^n thanks to the hypothesis that $f(x) - f(-x) \neq 0$ on all of S^n .

Proof. Since A is open in the topology of \mathbb{R}^n , for any $x \in A$, $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $B^n(x, \epsilon) \subset A$. In particular, since $m < n$, $\exists S \subset B^n(x, \epsilon) \subset A$ such that S is homeomorphic to S^m . Suppose for contradiction that there exists a continuous and injective function $f : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$. Then $f|_S : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is the restriction of f to S , and is also continuous and injective. Now take a homeomorphism $\phi : S^m \rightarrow S$ and consider the composition $f|_S \circ \phi : S^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$. This composition is continuous and injective, being a composition of continuous and injective functions. Moreover, it maps S^m to \mathbb{R}^m , contradicting the previous corollary, thereby proving the claim. \square

In particular, the previous theorem implies that no nonempty open set of \mathbb{R}^n is homeomorphic to an open set of \mathbb{R}^m for any $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \neq n$. Furthermore, if $n > m$, there is no subset of \mathbb{R}^m homeomorphic to a nonempty open set of \mathbb{R}^n .

Corollary 2.1.2: $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, there are no continuous maps $d : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ such that $d(-x) = -d(x) \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$.

Proof. Suppose that for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists a continuous $d : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ such that $d(-x) = -d(x) \forall x \in S^{n+1} \subset B^{n+1}$. Then the map:

$$f : S^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n \quad f(x_1, \dots, x_{n+2}) = \begin{cases} d(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}) & x_{n+2} \geq 0 \\ -d(-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1}) & x_{n+2} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

with $(x_1, \dots, x_{n+2}) \in S^{n+1} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+2}$. We show that this map is well defined, continuous, and satisfies $f(-x) = -f(x) \forall x \in S^{n+1}$. First we show that it is well defined, i.e., that if $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{n+2}) \in S^{n+1}$ then $(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}), (-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1}) \in B^{n+1}$, and that if $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}, 0) \in S^{n+1}$ then $d(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}) = -d(-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1})$. If $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{n+2}) \in S^{n+1}$ then $x_1^2 + \dots + x_{n+2}^2 = (-x_1)^2 + \dots + (-x_{n+2})^2 = 1$, so $x_1^2 + \dots + x_{n+1}^2 = (-x_1)^2 + \dots + (-x_{n+1})^2 = 1 - x_{n+2}^2 \leq 1$, hence $(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}), (-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1}) \in B^{n+1}$ by definition of B^{n+1} . If $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}, 0) \in S^{n+1}$, as shown above $(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}), (-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1}) \in B^{n+1}$, and by the hypothesis on d : $d(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}) = -d(-x_1, \dots, -x_{n+1})$.

Now \mathbb{R}^{n+2} is the topological product $\mathbb{R}^{n+1} \times \mathbb{R}$, and the projections: $p : \mathbb{R}^{n+2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ $q : \mathbb{R}^{n+2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous; in particular the restrictions $p|_Q : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, $p|_{Q'} : Q' \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, with $Q = S^{n+1} \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{n+2} : x_{n+2} \geq 0\}$ and $Q' = S^{n+1} \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{n+2} : x_{n+2} \leq 0\}$, are continuous. By construction $f|_Q = d \circ p|_Q$ and $f|_{Q'} = -d \circ (-p|_{Q'})$ ⁵. As one can see, $f|_Q$ and $f|_{Q'}$ are continuous as compositions of continuous functions, so $f : S^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ is continuous, since it is continuous on two closed subsets of S^{n+1} that cover it⁶.

Finally, we show that $f : S^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ as defined satisfies $f(-x) = -f(x) \forall x \in S^{n+1}$, contradicting Borsuk's theorem. If $x \in Q$ then $f(x) = d \circ p|_Q(x)$ and

⁴The n -dimensional ball of radius ϵ centered at x .

⁵We have already shown that f is well defined on S^{n+1} and therefore in particular on Q and Q' , i.e., $p|_Q(Q), p|_{Q'}(Q') \subset B^{n+1}$. Note also that $-p|_{Q'}$ is continuous, being the composition of the projection $p|_{Q'}$ and the inversion map in a vector space, both of which are continuous.

⁶The sets Q and Q' are defined as intersections of S^{n+1} with closed sets of \mathbb{R}^{n+2} that cover it, hence Q, Q' are closed in the subspace topology of S^{n+1} and cover it.

$-x \in Q'$, so $f(-x) = -d \circ (-p|_{Q'})(-x) = -d(-p|_{Q'}(-x))$; using the hypothesis on d , we get $f(-x) = d(p|_{Q'}(-x)) = d(-p|_Q(x)) = -d \circ p|_Q(x) = -f(x)$ ⁷. An analogous argument shows that $\forall x \in Q', f(-x) = -f(x)$. The contradiction with Borsuk's theorem gives the thesis. \square

Corollary 2.1.3: S^n is not a retract of B^{n+1} for $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, i.e., there are no continuous maps $d : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ such that $d(x) = x \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$.

Proof. By the previous corollary, there are no continuous maps $d : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ such that $d(-x) = -d(x) \forall x \in S^n$. In particular, if S^n were a retract of B^{n+1} , there would exist a continuous $\tilde{d} : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$ such that $\tilde{d}(x) = x \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$, i.e., $\tilde{d}(-x) = -x = -\tilde{d}(x) \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$, contradicting the previous corollary. \square

2.2 Brouwer's Fixed Point Theorem

Every continuous function $f : B^n \rightarrow B^n$ has at least one fixed point $x \in B^n$, i.e., $f(x) = x$.

Proof. Suppose for contradiction that $f(x) \neq x \forall x \in B^{n+1}$. Then the function:

$$d : B^{n+1} \rightarrow S^n$$

$$d(x) = x + \left(\frac{-\langle x-f(x); x \rangle + \sqrt{|\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|^2 - (\|x\|^2 - 1)(\|x-f(x)\|^2)}}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} \right) (x - f(x))$$

where $\langle *; * \rangle$ and $\| * \|$ denote the inner product and norm of \mathbb{R}^{n+1} induced on B^{n+1} .

We now show that: this function is well defined on B^{n+1} ; its image $d(B^{n+1})$ is contained in S^n ; it is continuous; and $d(x) = x \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$. That is, d is a retraction of B^{n+1} onto S^n , contradicting the previous corollary.

1) d is well defined on B^{n+1} : norms and inner products are well defined; the only issue is the denominator $\|x - f(x)\|^2$ and the definition of the square root. By hypothesis $\forall x \in B^{n+1}, f(x) \neq x \implies x - f(x) \neq 0 \implies \|x - f(x)\|^2 \neq 0$, so the denominator is defined at every point of B^{n+1} . The expression under the square root is: $|\langle x - f(x); x \rangle|^2 - (\|x\|^2 - 1)(\|x - f(x)\|^2)$, where $\|x\|^2 - 1 \leq 0 \forall x \in B^{n+1}$ by definition, so $-(\|x\|^2 - 1) \geq 0$, meaning the radicand is a sum of non-negative terms and hence non-negative. The square root is therefore well defined on all of B^{n+1} .

This shows that $d(x)$ is well defined on all of B^{n+1} .

2) $d(B^{n+1}) \subset S^n$: by construction, $d(x)$ is a linear combination of vectors in $\mathbb{R}^{n+1} \implies d(B^{n+1}) \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$.

Computing the Euclidean norm of $d(x)$, we obtain $\forall x \in B^{n+1}$:

⁷Using the property that $p|_{Q'}(-x) = p|_Q(x) \forall x \in Q$.

$$\begin{aligned} \|d(x)\|^2 &= \|x\|^2 + \frac{|\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|^2}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} + \frac{|\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|^2}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} - \|x\|^2 + 1 - \\ &\quad 2 \frac{\langle x-f(x); x \rangle \sqrt{A(x)}}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} - 2 \frac{|\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|^2}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} + 2 \frac{\langle x-f(x); x \rangle \sqrt{A(x)}}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} \end{aligned}$$

where $A(x) = |\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|^2 - (\|x\|^2 - 1)(\|x-f(x)\|^2)$.

All terms cancel except the 1, so $\|d(x)\|^2 = 1 \forall x \in B^{n+1}$, and by definition of S^n , $d(x) \in S^n \forall x \in B^{n+1}$.

3) d is continuous: d is obtained from continuous operations and compositions on B^{n+1} , hence it is continuous on B^{n+1} .

4) d is a retraction of B^{n+1} onto S^n : if $x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$ then $\|x\|^2 = 1$, giving:

$$d(x) = x + \left(\frac{-\langle x-f(x); x \rangle + |\langle x-f(x); x \rangle|}{\|x-f(x)\|^2} \right) (x - f(x))$$

It remains to prove that $\langle x-f(x); x \rangle \geq 0$:

$$\langle x-f(x); x \rangle = \|x\|^2 - \langle f(x); x \rangle = 1 - \langle f(x); x \rangle \geq 1 - \|x\| \cdot \|f(x)\| \geq 0$$

using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality $|\langle x; f(x) \rangle| \leq \|x\| \cdot \|f(x)\|$ and the facts that $\|x\| = 1$, $\|f(x)\| \leq 1$.

Therefore:

$$-\langle x-f(x); x \rangle \leq 0 \implies -\langle x-f(x); x \rangle + |\langle x-f(x); x \rangle| = 0 \implies d(x) = x \forall x \in S^n \subset B^{n+1}$$

Observe that the function $d(x)$, under the assumption that $f(x) \neq x \forall x \in B^{n+1}$, gives the intersection point of the line $r(t) = x + t(x-f(x))$ in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} with S^n , with $t \geq 0 \forall x \in B^{n+1}$.

3 Domain Invariance Theorem

Given $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ open and $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ injective and continuous, then $f(U)$ is open in \mathbb{R}^n .

This is precisely the Domain Invariance Theorem. Now take $f : B^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, a continuous and injective function, and show that $f(0)$ is an interior point of $f(B^n)$ with respect to the topology of \mathbb{R}^n .

The function $f : B^n \rightarrow f(B^n)$ is, by hypothesis, a continuous bijection between a compact space and a Hausdorff space, hence a homeomorphism. The inverse $f^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow B^n$ is continuous and defined on a closed⁸ subspace of \mathbb{R}^n (a normal topological space⁹). By the Tietze extension theorem, f^{-1} can be extended to a continuous function $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow B^n$ such that $g(x) = f^{-1}(x) \forall x \in f(B^n)$.

We recall the following result:

3.1 Tietze Extension Theorem

Let A be a closed subset of a normal space X , $B \subset \mathbb{R}$ a convex subspace, and $F : A \rightarrow B$ a continuous function. Then there exists a continuous $G : X \rightarrow B$ such that $G(y) = F(y) \forall y \in A$.

We claim that $\bar{f}^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ defined by $\bar{f}^{-1}(y) = f^{-1}(y) \forall y \in f(B^n)$ admits an extension $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ as above.

$\bar{f}^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous: indeed $\bar{f}^{-1} = i \circ f^{-1}$, i.e., the composition of f (continuous) with the inclusion $i : B^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, which is also continuous, so $\bar{f}^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous.

Now, \mathbb{R}^n is the topological product of \mathbb{R} taken n times, and by the definition of the product topology, $\bar{f}^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous if and only if all components $\bar{f}_i^{-1} = p_i \circ \bar{f}^{-1} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ are continuous (where p_i are the projections of \mathbb{R}^n onto the i -th component). Therefore for each i , $\bar{f}^{-1} * i : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the conditions for Tietze: the $\bar{f}^{-1} * i$ are continuous; defined on $f(B^n)$ closed in \mathbb{R}^n ; and have image in \mathbb{R} , which is convex. For each $i = 1, \dots, n$, denote by $g_i : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the continuous extension of $\bar{f}^{-1} * i : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. All these functions are continuous by construction, so the function $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ defined by $g(y) = (g_1(y), \dots, g_n(y)) \forall y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous; moreover $g(y) = \bar{f}^{-1}(y) = f^{-1}(y) \forall y \in f(B^n)$.

⁸ f^{-1} is defined on $f(B^n) \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, the image of a continuous function on the compact set B^n , so $f(B^n)$ is compact in \mathbb{R}^n , i.e., closed and bounded.

⁹ A topological space is normal if: for every pair of disjoint closed sets (A, B) , there exists a pair of disjoint open sets (C, D) such that $A \subset C$ and $B \subset D$. In particular, \mathbb{R}^n is normal for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

3.2 Lemma 3.2.1 (Zero Stability)

Given $\tilde{g} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ a continuous function such that $\|g(y) - \tilde{g}(y)\| \leq 1$ $\forall y \in f(B^n)$. Then \tilde{g} has at least one zero, i.e., $\exists \tilde{y} \in f(B^n)$ such that $\tilde{g}(\tilde{y}) = 0$.

Let g denote the extension constructed above \bar{f}^{-1} . Since $g(x) = \bar{f}^{-1}(y) = f^{-1}(y) \forall y \in f(B^n)$, for $f(0) \in f(B^n)$ we have $0 = f^{-1}(f(0)) = \bar{f}^{-1}(f(0)) = g(f(0))$, i.e., for some $\tilde{y} \in f(B^n)$, $g(\tilde{y}) = 0$.

The proof follows from Brouwer's Fixed Point Theorem.

Proof of lemma: consider the function $h : B^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, $h(x) = x - \tilde{g}(f(x))$.

This function is well defined on B^n , since the image of B^n under f , namely $f(B^n)$, lies in the domain of \tilde{g} .

Moreover $h(x)$ is continuous as a composition of continuous functions; and by definition of f^{-1} and g , $g(f(x)) = f^{-1}(f(x)) = x \forall x \in B^n$, so $h(x) = g(f(x)) - \tilde{g}(f(x)) \forall x \in B^n$.

Using the hypothesis $\|g(y) - \tilde{g}(y)\| \leq 1 \forall y \in f(B^n)$, we get $\|h(x)\| = \|g(f(x)) - \tilde{g}(f(x))\| \leq 1 \forall x \in B^n$, so $h(x) \in B^n \forall x \in B^n$. Restricting the codomain of h to B^n , we have a continuous function $\bar{h} : B^n \rightarrow B^n$ with $\bar{h}(x) = h(x) \forall x \in B^n$. By Brouwer's fixed point theorem, $\exists \tilde{x} \in B^n$ such that $\bar{h}(\tilde{x}) = \tilde{x}$, hence $\tilde{x} - \tilde{g}(f(\tilde{x})) = \tilde{x}$, i.e., $\tilde{g}(f(\tilde{x})) = 0$. Setting $\tilde{y} = f(\tilde{x}) \in f(B^n)$ proves the claim. □

3.3 Domain Invariance Theorem

Given $f : B^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ a continuous and injective function. Then $f(0)$ belongs to the interior of $f(B^n)$ with respect to the topology of \mathbb{R}^n .

Suppose for contradiction that the Domain Invariance Theorem fails, i.e., $\exists f : B^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ continuous and injective such that $f(0)$ does not belong to the interior of $f(B^n)$.

We show that this contradicts the Zero Stability Lemma.

Since g (the extension of \bar{f}^{-1}) is continuous, $\exists \delta > 0$ such that $\|g(y) - g(f(0))\| = \|g(y)\| \leq 0.1 \forall y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $\|y - f(0)\| < \delta$.

Since we assumed that $f(0)$ does not belong to the interior of $f(B^n)$, $\exists c \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\|c - f(0)\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$ with $c \notin f(B^n)$, and we get:

$$\|g(y)\| < 0.1 \forall y \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ such that } \|y - c\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$$

since if $\|y - c\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$ then $\|y - f(0)\| \leq \|y - c\| + \|c - f(0)\| < \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{\delta}{2} = \delta$. Define $\Sigma := \Sigma_1 \cup \Sigma_2$, with $\Sigma_1 := \{y \in f(B^n) : \|y - c\| \geq \frac{\delta}{2}\}$ and $\Sigma_2 := \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|y - c\| = \frac{\delta}{2}\}$. By construction, Σ is compact, being the union of compact sets¹⁰, and $f(0) \notin \Sigma$ since $\|f(0) - c\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$.

Consider the function:

$$\Phi : f(B^n) \rightarrow \Sigma \quad \Phi(y) := \max\left(\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}, 1\right)y - \max\left(\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|} - 1, 0\right)c$$

¹⁰ Σ_1 is compact as the preimage of a closed set of \mathbb{R} under a continuous function, contained in the compact $f(B^n)$. Σ_2 is compact because it is the preimage of a closed set of \mathbb{R} under a continuous function (hence closed), and also bounded in \mathbb{R}^n ; a closed bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^n is compact.

This is well defined since $c \notin f(B^n) \implies \|y - c\| \neq 0 \forall y \in f(B^n)$, and it is continuous as it is built from continuous operations. It remains to show that $\Phi(y) \in \Sigma \forall y \in f(B^n)$: if $\max(\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}, 1) = 1$ then $\max(\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|} - 1, 0) = 0$ so $\|\Phi(y) - c\| = \|y - c\| \geq \frac{\delta}{2}$, hence $y = \Phi(y) \in \Sigma_1 \subset \Sigma$; if $\max(\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}, 1) = \frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}$ then $\Phi(y) = \frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}y - (\frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|} - 1)c \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\|\Phi(y) - c\| = \frac{\delta}{2\|y-c\|}\|y - c\| = \frac{\delta}{2}$, so $\Phi(y) \in \Sigma_2 \subset \Sigma$.

By construction, the extension g never vanishes on Σ_1 ¹¹; by continuity of g and compactness of Σ_1 , $g(\Sigma_1)$ is compact and hence closed and bounded in \mathbb{R}^n , not containing zero, so $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $g(\Sigma_1) \cap \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon) = \emptyset$ ¹².

By compactness of Σ and continuity of g , we apply the Stone-Weierstrass approximation theorem: $\forall \sigma > 0$ there exists a ‘vector-valued polynomial’¹³ $P : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\|P(y) - g(y)\| < \sigma \forall y \in \Sigma$.

Choosing $\bar{\sigma} = \min(\frac{\epsilon}{2}, 0.1)$, we obtain $P(y) \neq 0 \forall y \in \Sigma_1$; otherwise $\exists y_0 \in \Sigma_1$ with $P(y_0) = 0$, giving $\|g(y_0)\| < \bar{\sigma}$ and $g(y_0) \in \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon)$, contradicting $g(\Sigma_1) \cap \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon) = \emptyset$. In general, however, P might vanish on Σ_2 ; we now eliminate this possibility.

It remain to observe that Σ_2 ¹⁴ has Lebesgue measure zero in \mathbb{R}^n , which implies $P(\Sigma_2)$ has measure zero in \mathbb{R}^n . Indeed, $P : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is polynomial hence C^1 and locally Lipschitz. Since Σ_2 is compact, the restriction $P|_{\Sigma_2}$ is Lipschitz on a compact neighborhood of Σ_2 . Lipschitz maps preserve sets of measure zero, so $P(\Sigma_2)$ has measure zero in \mathbb{R}^n . Since $P(\Sigma_2)$ has measure zero, there exists $d \in \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \min(\frac{\epsilon}{2}, 0.1)) \setminus P(\Sigma_2)$ ¹⁵, so taking the polynomial $P'(y) = P(y) - d$ for $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we get: $0 \notin P'(\Sigma_2)$ since $d \notin P(\Sigma_2)$, and $\|P'(y) - g(y)\| = \|P(y) - d - g(y)\| \leq \|P(y) - g(y)\| + \|d\| < 2\min(\frac{\epsilon}{2}, 0.1) \forall y \in \Sigma$, which on Σ_1 gives $P'(y) \neq 0 \forall y \in \Sigma_1$; otherwise $\exists \bar{y} \in \Sigma_1$ with $P'(\bar{y}) = 0$, so $g(\bar{y}) \in \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \min(\epsilon, 0.2)) \subset \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon)$, contradicting the choice of ϵ .

We therefore have $\|P'(y) - g(y)\| < \min(\epsilon, 0.2)$ and $P'(y) \neq 0 \forall y \in \Sigma$.

Consider the function:

$$\tilde{g} : f(B^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \quad \tilde{g}(y) := P'(\Phi(y))$$

This function is continuous as a composition of continuous functions, and never vanishes by construction.

By definition of Φ , $\tilde{g}(y) = P'(y) \forall y \in \Sigma_1$, so $\|g(y) - \tilde{g}(y)\| = \|g(y) - P'(y)\| < \min(\epsilon, 0.2) \forall y \in \Sigma_1$. Taking the complement of Σ_1 in $f(B^n)$, i.e., $f(B^n) \setminus \Sigma_1 = y \in f(B^n) : \|y - c\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$, by definition of δ we have $\|g(y)\| < 0.1 \forall y$ with $\|y - c\| < \frac{\delta}{2}$, in particular on $f(B^n) \setminus \Sigma_1$; also $\Phi(y) \in \Sigma_2 \forall y \in f(B^n) \setminus \Sigma_1$, so by continuity of g : $\|g(\Phi(y))\| \leq 0.1 \forall y \in f(B^n) \setminus \Sigma_1$. Therefore $\|g(y) - \tilde{g}(y)\| \leq$

¹¹Because $f(0) \notin \Sigma \supset \Sigma_1$, and on $\Sigma_1 \subset f(B^n)$, g is injective with $g(f(0)) = 0$, so $g(y) \neq 0 \forall y \in \Sigma_1$.

¹²The existence of such a ball is guaranteed because \mathbb{R}^n is normal, and both $g(\Sigma_1)$ and 0 are closed in \mathbb{R}^n , so there exist disjoint open sets A, B with $g(\Sigma_1) \subset A$ and $0 \subset B$. Since B is open and contains 0 , $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $\overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon) \subset B$, hence $g(\Sigma_1) \cap \overset{\circ}{B}^n(0, \epsilon) = \emptyset$.

¹³By ‘vector polynomial’ we mean a function $P : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ where each component is a polynomial $p : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

¹⁴Which is the $(n - 1)$ -sphere with center c and radius $\frac{\delta}{2}$

¹⁵Sets of measure zero in \mathbb{R}^n have empty interior.

$\|g(y)\| + \|\tilde{g}(\Phi(y))\| + \|\tilde{g}(\Phi(y)) - \tilde{g}(y)\| < 0.2 + \min(\epsilon, 0.2) < 0.4 \forall y \in f(B^n) \setminus \Sigma_1$.
 We conclude that $\|g(y) - \tilde{g}(y)\| < 0.4 \forall y \in f(B^n)$, but combined with $g(y) \neq 0 \forall y \in f(B^n)$, this contradicts the Zero Stability Lemma. The theorem is proved.

□

3.4 Conclusions

In general, if $f : B^n(a, r) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous and injective, then $f(a) \in f(B^n(a, r))$. This follows from the fact that any two balls in \mathbb{R}^n are homeomorphic; the verification is left to the reader. Now take an open set $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n$; by local compactness of \mathbb{R}^n and the fact that U is open, $\forall x \in U \exists \epsilon_x > 0$ such that $B^n(x, \epsilon_x) \subset U$. Thus, given a continuous and injective function $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, its restriction to each ball $B^n(x, \epsilon_x)$ (i.e., $f|_{B^n(x, \epsilon_x)} : B^n(x, \epsilon_x) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$) is continuous and injective. By the theorem proved above, $\forall x \in U$, $f(x)$ is an interior point of $f|_{B^n(x, \epsilon_x)}(B^n(x, \epsilon_x)) \subset f(U)$, hence also an interior point of $f(U)$. Every point of $f(U)$ is interior, so $f(U)$ is open. Therefore, a continuous and injective function $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with U open maps open subsets of U (which are also open in \mathbb{R}^n) to open subsets of \mathbb{R}^n , i.e., f is continuous, injective, and open; hence a homeomorphism onto its image.

Continuous and injective functions $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with U open are homeomorphisms onto their image, and in particular embeddings.

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